

careables.org

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White Paper on Legal Guidelines

Common legal challenges in OSH for healthcare

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1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Careables.org is an online platform serving as a central hub for sharing knowledge for reproduction and self-creation of customized healthcare solutions. It encompasses a repository for the storage of open hardware projects' technical documentation, and it shall represent an environment where individuals with particular needs, caregivers, healthcare professionals, makers and designers, work collaboratively online in order to create custom-made healthcare solutions – *careables*¹. The white paper tackles:

- **Privacy and data protection.** Developing an OSH solution may entail the processing of personal and health data of individuals. This may happen at different stages of design and co-creation of a solution, namely while designing or prototyping the solution, or while uploading the related documentation on the careables.org platform. During all these stages, each of the stakeholders involved should take into account their respective role in the processing, the legal basis, and the purposes of the data processing activities. Moreover, data should be processed in a lawful, transparent, and fair manner while technical and organisational measures necessary to ensure the security of the processing need to be in place. Individuals should always be informed of any processing of their personal data, and data protection by design approach should be applied from the very first design phase of the solution.
- **Intellectual property rights.** Designers and makers of an OSH solution should be aware of the EU/national copyright law applicable to the documentation, its implications, given rights, and duration of the protection in order to be able to adequately assess and chose licensing terms. Copyright licences cannot be applied to hardware. Therefore, patent licences should be consulted.
- **Liability.** OSH co-design and co-creation often involves many stakeholders which is likely to lead to an overlap of liability responsibilities. As stakeholders are often located in different geographical areas, different liability frameworks may become applicable. As a general rule, liability requirements (stemming from the product liability law and tort law) have to be applied on a case-by-case basis.
- **Medical devices regulation.** In order to assess whether a specific healthcare solution has to comply with the EU medical devices legislation, makers and designers should take into account the notion of 'manufacturer', the definition of a 'medical device', and the purpose of an OSH solution.

¹ Biasin E, Kamenjasevic E, D6.1 Legal and ethical inventory and in-depth analysis (2018), D6.2 Implementation of the legal and ethical requirements (2019), available at: <https://www.careables.org/resources/>

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List of abbreviations

CC	Creative Commons
DPO	Data Protection Officer
EU	European Union
KUL	KU Leuven
MDL	Medical devices legislation
OSH	Open-Source Hardware
OSS	Open Source Software
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
WP	Work Package

Introduction

PURPOSE OF THE DOCUMENT

Purpose of this White Paper is to map common legal challenges of Open-Source Hardware for healthcare. It addresses privacy and data protection, intellectual property rights, liability, and medical devices legislation. The White Paper is addressed to makers, designers, and healthcare professionals involved in co-design as co-creation of open-source hardware healthcare solutions, fablabs, as well as DPOs and local networks for industry representatives.

STRUCTURE OF THE DOCUMENT

The White Paper is divided into five chapters. Background sets the scene for the general outline of the paper, describes open collaborative platforms, and briefly explains the notion of 'open-source hardware'. The following chapter deals with the common legal challenges associated with open collaborative platforms and it **addresses privacy and data protection issues, intellectual property rights, liability risks, and new requirements of medical devices regulation** in order to provide the designers and makers community with the outline of the main legal issues they may face when collaborating with other makers and developing new solutions. Conclusions provide recommendations for makers based on a number of selected hypothesis.

Background

WHAT ARE THE OPEN COLLABORATIVE PLATFORMS?

Increase of connectivity, combined with the democratisation of design and fabrication tools have opened the possibility for individuals to collaborate in new digital environments. Collaborative innovation is a phenomenon that has rapidly diffused around the world: multiple stakeholders progressively engage in sharing non-appropriated innovation and create new projects, technologies and solutions through open collaborative platforms. Open collaborative platforms are becoming a mean to empower individuals to share projects and ideas online, and even co-create new products with other users around the world.

Over the last years, many initiatives have kicked-off (such as Thingiverse, Github, Wevolver, or, with a focus on healthcare Instructables, e-Nable²). Their common objective is fostering collaborative innovation online. Community and society as a whole benefit from this kind of novel interaction as these collaborations enhance and empower individuals to access healthcare solutions regardless of their physical location. In that regard, objectives of the open collaborative platforms support advancement of the United Nations (UN) Sustainable Development Goals (SDG), namely the **SDG n. 3 "Good Health and Well Being"**³ – with particular focus on the Target 3.4 ("By 2030, reduce by one third premature mortality from non-communicable diseases through prevention and treatment and *promote mental health and well-being*") and Target 3.8 ("Achieve universal health coverage, including financial risk protection, access to quality essential health-care services and access to safe, effective, quality and affordable essential medicines and vaccines for all").

² See respectively: <https://www.thingiverse.com>; <https://github.com>; <https://www.wevolver.com>; <https://www.instructables.com>; <http://enablingthefuture.org/> accessed 20 November 2019.

³ See UN website on SDG: <https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/?menu=1300> (accessed 13 December 2019).

[Careables.org](https://careables.org) is an example of how users can collaboratively work online. It is a platform where designers, makers, healthcare professionals, and users may share their knowledge to create a specific healthcare solution suitable for a particular healthcare need. Careables.org is a place where digital social innovation happens, and where users and communities collaborate to co-create solutions for healthcare needs by using advantages of new digital technologies. A novelty of this platform is that it provides only fully documented and customized healthcare solutions. Furthermore, the platform promotes the respect of main legal (such as privacy, data protection, law of medical devices, intellectual property rights, liability) and ethical requirements, as relevant in Europe.

The key stakeholders in open collaborative platforms in healthcare

*There is a wide array of **stakeholders** contributing to the co-design and co-creation of healthcare solutions through a collaborative platform (such as careables.org). The main categories of individuals that usually interact and engage with open collaborative platforms are:*

***Individuals/patients** in need of a particular healthcare solution.*

***Healthcare professionals** supporting individuals/patients in finding the most suitable healthcare solutions for their needs.*

***Designers, engineers and developers** wanting to share their projects online and populate them.*

***Makers** locally replicating a specific healthcare solution.*

WHAT IS 'OPEN-SOURCE HARDWARE'?

Individuals involved in platforms like Careables.org use open source tools to ensure that solutions and ideas they share can be freely accessed worldwide. Many users are already familiar with the Open Source Software (OSS) movement, which has been the first and major example of collaborative innovation in the last decades. A new frontier of the open source movement is **Open-Source Hardware (OSH)**.

While OSS refers to the open use and distribution of computer software and source code, in OSH open innovation mechanisms move towards the realm of hardware and tangible objects. Similar to OSS, the underlying principle of OSH is to generate open and accessible knowledge. On a level of a collaborative platform, this implies licensing of the design specification of a physical object in such a way that said object can be studied, modified, created and distributed by anyone, anywhere, and anytime. Knowledge material and source files (such as instructions, schematics, blueprints, CAD files) are rendered **available to the community** under licenses according to which (and depending on their specific terms) users may add features, modify the physical design of the object itself, share modifications, or similar.

Common legal challenges in OSH for healthcare

CONTEXT

Since the phenomenon of collaborative platforms and OSH are relatively novel subjects in law and given the global reach of the platforms, it has become burdensome for the stakeholders to have a **clear understanding of the legal challenges** they may face. The following chapters will try to provide answers to some of them. In particular, those designing OSH solutions often wonder what kind of legal requirements they should take into account and what could be the legal consequences of using a collaborative platform for sharing projects and ideas. Could makers and designers be held accountable for the misuse of an object that has been manufactured according to the information and instructions they provided on a collaborative platform? Or, what if someone gets injured from the use of the object shared on the platform? What if a third party is injured by the object that has been manufactured following the indications provided on the platform?

Source: <https://www.welder.app/careables.org/open.source.leg/master/tree>

PRIVACY AND DATA PROTECTION

The development of an OSH item may entail the processing of personal (and also health) data of an individual. This is may happen at different stages of design and co-creation of a solution:

From an abstract idea to prototyping: when an individual (patient, or person with a special need) meets with a team of designers, engineers, makers with the support of a healthcare professional to explain his or her need, it is likely that an amount of information relating to his or her health will be shared. This kind of information has to be properly processed according to the requirements foreseen by the law (GDPR). Similarly, when 'FabLabs' or a Makerspace organise thematic events to prototype specific objects in the presence of persons with specific needs, it is important to be aware that the processing of personal data may occur, and the requirements prescribed by the law have to be respected.

Design of the healthcare solution: designing a healthcare solution may entail the evaluation of aspects pertaining to the functioning of the solution itself. While it is not a common feature that a given solution processes personal data, it should not be excluded this may actually occur. To give an example, a healthcare solution that monitors heart rates or insulin rates might be subject to data protection legal requirements if the heart or insulin rate is considered to be personal data.

Uploading a healthcare solution: the purpose of an open collaborative platform is being a common hub to share ideas and documentation. When uploading a CAD file or instructions contains information about the patient or the individual for which the solution is created, only the necessary information may be disclosed on the platform.

Sources: <https://www.welder.app/gioia.chi/easy.cut/master/tree>

Sources: <https://www.welder.aoo/careables.org/adaoptable.drinking.ai>

Privacy and data protection have to be considered for development of an open healthcare solution. Each stakeholder should question what is his or her **role** in the data processing and what is the **legal basis** for the processing of personal data. All operations, from prototyping to designing and uploading documentation on the platform, should be done by paying attention to privacy and data protection laws. Personal data should be processed only if **strictly necessary** for achieving the purpose for which they are being collected, and only as **relevant** to such purpose.

Data should be processed in a **lawful, transparent, and fair manner**. The key stakeholders must put in place the technical and organisational measures that are necessary to ensure **security** of the processing of personal data. Patients and individuals should always be **informed** of any processing of their personal data, deriving from an initiative, a prototyping session, or the upload of any personal information pertaining to him or her on the collaborative platform. Every stakeholder involved in the material development of a healthcare solution should be aware that privacy must be taken care of as from the first design steps of the solution (**data protection by design principle**).

INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS

While developing a specific OSH solution, IPR-related questions will arise. Therefore, during the design phase of an OSH, designers and makers should agree on the ownership rights, exclusivity, and licensing terms. They should also be aware of the EU/national copyright law applicable to the documentation, its implications, their rights, and duration of the protection in order to be able to adequately assess and choose licensing terms. Moreover, within this phase, designers and makers should evaluate whether they can obtain a patent protection, as well as the implications, rights, duration, limitations, and fees of having it applied to their healthcare solution.

Once the documentation for the OSH is drafted, it enjoys the copyright protection. To meet the openness and the free-use goals embedded in the philosophy of careables⁴ as mentioned above, designers and makers should consider the use of certain licences, such as Creative Commons (CC). The application of a copyright license on a documentation is possible as a subsequent phase followed by the initial acquisition of copyright protection.

Copyright licenses cannot be applied to hardware (i.e., a physical object) as it is not a subject to such protection but to, for instance, a patent or design protection. If designers and makers obtain a patent protection, they may, as a second step, license the hardware under terms they wish to apply. If they do not obtain a patent protection, designers and makers do not need to apply a hardware license to it

⁴ A careable is an open solution that aims to improve the quality of life for people with unmet particular needs or facing physical limitations. Careables are often co-designed, replicable, accessible, adjustable and shareable online using digital technologies. Careables is a relatively new category, that promises more readily customized solutions and a more horizontal and collaborative approach to health and care.

and everyone may be free to use such kind of hardware freely, as long as they respect the copyright license obtained for the documentation. Importantly, copyright protection exists independently to a patent or design protection. In other words, even if you do not obtain patent protection, the EU copyright requirements apply by default to the documentation.

LIABILITY

Some of the most pressing questions in the OSH community that are not answered yet are 'Will I be liable if any damage occurs to a person?', or, 'What are the risks for a maker, a designer, a healthcare professional, a caregiver if something goes wrong'?

In the frame of the OSH co-design and co-creation through collaborative platforms, many stakeholders are involved. The interplay of these subjects is likely to lead to an overlap of liability responsibilities. Furthermore, these stakeholders are often located in different geographical areas, and given the different contexts (i.e., commercial, non-commercial, household) from which they are operating, different liability frameworks may be applicable. These could range from civil law, product liability law, medical devices law, intellectual property law, privacy and data protection law, and other. As a general remark, it should be highlighted that every damage or a contractual non-compliance has to be evaluated on a **case-by-case basis**. Nonetheless, in order to apply the 'rule of thumbs' to questions that affect daily activities of the OSH stakeholders, the following may be relevant:

An individual or a legal entity may be held liable under **product liability law** when a product is defective and causes personal injury to an individual. If the product is defective, the manufacturer might be held liable even if he or she has not been negligent in manufacturing that defective product (as to the **strict liability doctrine**). However, the interpretation of product liability law may become fuzzy

when makers and designers are involved. That is because in theory, strict liability applies to products that have been *industrially* produced, when the product was manufactured for sale or *economic purposes* or in course of the producer's business. This rule is therefore challenged by the novel role of makers and designers not perfectly fitting in the previous scenarios. In a do-it-yourself (DIY) environment, makers and designers may not be necessarily regular sellers (only), rather (also) hobbyists performing household activities.

At the moment, there are no clear rules for makers and designers nor significant EU case law in this regard. Nonetheless, as a general rule, it may be inferred that strict liability rules should always be evaluated on a case-by-case basis, and these rules could reasonably be applied when an entity is a regular seller, rather than an occasional one.

Moreover, makers and designers are generally bound to diligence standards for the activities they perform. Hence, if a damage occurs, under certain circumstances they may be held liable according to tort law. As a general rule, tort law liability follows when a **duty of care** is breached. Thus, makers and designers should apply adequate standards of diligence while co-designing and co-developing their projects.

Source: <https://www.careables.org/>

MEDICAL DEVICES REGULATION

Does the European legislation apply to an OSH solution that has been shared on a collaborative platform? What should a maker do when he or she wants to reproduce a healthcare item from the design files shared on a platform? The essential points to facilitate the orientation of OSH stakeholders within the complex legal environment of the EU medical devices legislation (MDL) are listed below.

Medical device is any device (or instrument, software, implant or any article) intended to be used for medical purposes. Medical devices can be of various kinds. They may range, for instance, from non-invasive devices (e.g. cervical collars, walking aids, wheelchairs) to invasive devices (e.g. tracheal tubes, long term corrective contact lenses) to surgically invasive devices (e.g. breast implants, prosthetic heart valves). Medical devices may be also 'connected-to-network', such as insulin pumps, heart defibrillators as well as pacemakers. European law classifies medical devices depending on the risks they may have for patients and foresees specific technical requirements aimed at ensuring the **safety of patients**. The full application of the MDL depends on the occurrence of a variety of factors. Below are some key **recommendations** to preliminarily guide makers and designers in assessing legal context of a device they are operating⁵:

⁵ Even if the analysis of these factors might appear swift and not requiring much effort, it is worth underlining that it is not an easy task. Furthermore, it should be stressed that the identification of the applicable requirements and laws might be facilitated with the support of a medical device legal professional.

Identify the personal scope: makers and designers, when co-designing and co-producing a device, should question whether they fall under a definition of a 'manufacturer'⁶ within the meaning of the EU MDL and in what kind of business-related context they operate.

Check the material scope: before establishing applicable MDL requirements, it is necessary to evaluate whether the healthcare solution falls under the definition of a medical device within the meaning of MDL. Not every item will be considered a medical device, hence, it is important to assess (1) the nature of the device, (2) its intended usage and, (3) its principal intended action.

Determine the purpose of the device: makers and designers should evaluate whether the item is intended to be principally used for a specific medical purpose or not, as determined by the law. As an example, a medical purpose may be the treatment or the compensation of an injury or the replacement or modification of the anatomy.

⁶ According to the EU MDL, a manufacturer is whoever has the responsibility for the design, manufacture, packaging and labelling of a device before its placing on the market. A more extensive outline of the matter may be found in the reports on legal and ethical requirements of the Made4You project: see E. Kamenjasevic, E. Biasin, 'Made4You Deliverable 6.1 Legal and ethical inventory and in-depth analysis' (2018) and E. Biasin, E. Kamenjasevic, 'Made4You Deliverable 6.2 Implementation of the legal and ethical requirements' (2019).

Conclusions

The White Paper provides an overview of the common legal challenges that makers, designers, healthcare professional, and individuals usually face when co-designing and co-creating OSH solutions for health and care. Privacy and data protection requirements, intellectual property management issues, tort law and liability aspects as well as medical devices legislation are key factors that should be duly taken into account in this context.

As illustrated above, the grey areas in the OSH field with regard to the legal requirements result in uncertainty for the stakeholders involved. To fill this gap, this White Paper provides key recommendations for the stakeholders by explaining, in plain terms, the general principles of the laws applicable to the OSH. Next to these key recommendations, the White Paper finally proposes an Infographic containing 'Recommendations for makers developing OSH for healthcare', that may be found in the Annex of the document.

Annex

Recommendations for makers developing OSH for healthcare

	HACKING an existing solution	UPLOADING a DESIGN on a Collaborative Platform	HOUSEHOLD Activity	COMMERCIAL Activity
HYPOTHESIS	<p>The solution can be mass produced or manufactured on a small scale and distributed by a third party (i.e., a non profit organization, a tech for good company or by any future social enterprise).</p>			
RECOMMENDATIONS	<p>The involved stakeholders may be strictly responsible for the design and manufacturing of the solutions. They should evaluate whether and how to meet the legal requirements foreseen by medical devices legislation.</p>			

This table presents a selected number of hypothesis and a non-exhaustive recommendations for OSH Makers and Designers for the explanatory purposes. These hypothesis may occur jointly or separately. The table is a 'remix' of 'Open Source Medical Devices. A Visual Guide for Makers'.